

A study on the correlation of BMI and Abnormal Uterine Bleeding among Premenopausal age group women

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Abstract:

Introduction: Abnormal Uterine Bleeding (AUB) is a common presentation in Gynecology Outpatient department. AUB may be associated with pain and discomfort, affecting the quality of life, productivity and cause economic burden to the self and the family due to medical or surgical intervention. Prevalence of obesity is in concerning rise and it is been suggested as one of the risk factor for endometrial pathology. **Objective:** To assess the association between BMI and Bleeding pattern, the endometrial thickness and histopathological finding in AUB among Premenopausal women. **Methods:** After excluding the major confounding factors, 100 women with AUB were included. Baseline data were collected and Body mass index (BMI) was calculated. The participants with 18.5 - 24.9Kg/m² and ≥ 25 Kg/m² were considered as normal weight and overweight respectively. All the participants were subjected to pelvic ultrasound examination and endometrial biopsy. **Result:** Around 66% were overweight and common bleeding pattern is heavy bleeding, which was statistically significant with increasing BMI. Mean Endometrial thickness (ET) was 15.33mm and showed association with overweight. No significance found between varied histopathological finding and increasing BMI. **Conclusion:** We found increased BMI among Premenopausal women with AUB and that recommends the need to include weight reduction as a part of comprehensive management of AUB.

Keywords: Abnormal uterine bleeding, endometrial thickness, Body mass index, Premenopausal women

INTRODUCTION:

Abnormal Uterine bleeding (AUB) is an extensive term used to define any deviation from normal menstruation with abnormality in volume, regularity, duration and frequency of flow. AUB occurs in 9% to 14% women approaching Gynecology outpatient department, which affects their quality of life since menarche to menopause.¹ AUB diagnosis requires comprehensive approach with detailed medical history, clinical examination with laboratory blood analysis, imaging technique and histopathological analysis. Different bleeding pattern categorized into frequent or infrequent, prolonged or shortened, regular or irregular and

heavy or scanty flow helps in finding the cause of AUB. Moreover, management of AUB in India with wide health care diversity needs comprehensive uniform guidelines.²

Global recognition of increasing obesity is documented since the past 20 years.³ Obesity is associated with abnormal menstrual pattern and it's an important risk factor for development of complex hyperplasia or endometrial cancer.⁴ Bariatric Surgery done for Obese women proved positive effect in Anovulation resulting in Abnormal uterine bleeding.⁵ Likewise, weight reduction showed 50% resumption to normal menstruation in Obese women.⁶ Meta-analysis done in China proved overweight and obese women have 1.43 times increase in chance of developing endometrial cancer compared to normal weight women.⁷

As mostly, endometrial cancer occurs in postmenopausal women, it is not recognized widely that obesity is an important risk factor for endometrial hyperplasia or cancer among symptomatic premenopausal women.³ Considering the increasing prevalence of obesity, this study was proposed to be conducted among premenopausal women to understand the role of obesity as risk factor for endometrial pathology.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

The aim of the study was to assess the association between BMI and Bleeding pattern, Endometrial thickness (ET) and Histopathological finding in Abnormal Uterine Bleeding among Premenopausal women.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

An observational cross-sectional study was conducted in a Tertiary care hospital. Ethical committee approval was obtained before the start of the study. Women attending the Gynecology OPD with complaints of Abnormal Menstrual bleeding in the age group of 40 to 55 (Premenopausal) were included. Women with confirmed pregnancy, structural genital tract abnormality, pelvic inflammatory disease, women with thyroid, liver and renal disorders, coagulation disorders and on drugs inducing bleeding were excluded. Women not willing to participate in the study were also excluded. The study was conducted for a period of three months, consisting of 100 Premenopausal age group women after obtaining informed written consent from them.

The sample size was calculated using Open epi software version 3 with estimated proportion of 60%⁸ and at 5% level of significance. The minimum sample size calculated was 98 and the study was conducted among 100 premenopausal women.

Baseline information like age, socioeconomic status, parity, diet pattern, physical activity, presence of chronic diseases, use of regular medication or oral contraceptive pills were collected from participants. Detailed Menstrual (bleeding pattern as per FIGO classification), obstetric, medical and surgical history were obtained and clinical examination was done.

FIGO 2018 definition for bleeding pattern:²

Frequency: Infrequent - > 38 days; Frequent - < 24 days

Duration: Normal \leq 8 days; Prolonged > 8 days

Regularity: Regular \leq 7 – 9 days; Irregular \geq 8-9 days

Volume (only patient determined): light, normal and heavy (heavy bleeding interferes with women's daily activity)

Intermenstrual bleeding: bleeding between cyclically regular onset of menses

All the 100 participants were subjected to height and weight measurement and BMI is calculated using the formula Kg/m^2 . Blood samples were collected for laboratory analysis of complete hemogram, liver function, Renal function, thyroid function and coagulation disorder. All the participants were subjected to Pelvic ultrasound examination followed by endometrial biopsy. Biopsy were studied for histopathological variation of endometrium in Abnormal Uterine Bleeding.

The data were entered in excel and analyzed using SPSS Software version 21. Descriptive and analytical statistical methods were used. All the categorical variables were presented in frequency (as the sample is 100, both frequency and percentage will be same). Chi-square test were used to assess the association between different categorical variables.

RESULTS:

Baseline Characteristics:

Among 100 women, 46 participants belong to 45 – 49 age group, 33% and 32% belongs to middle and upper middle socioeconomic status as per Modified BG Prasad scale. There were 32 vegetarian and 68 non vegetarian in the study group. Among the study group 48% had relatively active in their physical activity. Around 77% had more than one child and 66% had BMI more than 25. No underweight women in the present study. (as per WHO BMI Classification: Underweight - $< 18.4 \text{ Kg/m}^2$; Normal weight - $18.5 - 24.9 \text{ Kg/m}^2$; Overweight - $25 - 29.9 \text{ Kg/m}^2$ and Obese $\geq 30 \text{ Kg/m}^2$)⁹ (Table 1)

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of Participants (n=100)

Variables	Frequency	
Age	40-44	39
	45-49	46
	50 and above	15
Socioeconomic Status (Modified BG Prasad Classification 2023)	Upper	12
	Upper middle	32
	Middle	33
	Lower middle	15
	Lower	8
Diet	Vegetarian	32
	Non- vegetarian	68
Physical Activity	Inactive	32
	Relatively Active	48
	Active	20
Parity	Single Parity	23
	Multiparous	77
BMI	18.5 - 24.9	34
	≥ 25	66

Bleeding pattern in Abnormal Uterine Bleeding:

Around 40% of women present with Heavy menstrual bleeding and 24% present with both heavy and prolonged bleeding. Only 10% presented with intermenstrual bleeding (Fig:1). Women with lower BMI had Scanty or Infrequent bleeding and women with increased BMI had heavy Bleeding, which is statistically significant with p value < 0.05. No statistical significance proved for frequent bleeding, intermenstrual bleeding and heavy and prolonged bleeding in association with BMI (Table 2)

Figure 1: Distribution of Bleeding pattern in Abnormal Uterine Bleeding: (n=100)

Table 2: Association between Pattern of Bleeding in AUB and BMI

Pattern of Bleeding	BMI		Total	Chi-square Value	p- value
	18.5 - 24.9 Kg/m ²	≥ 25 Kg/m ²			
Frequent Bleeding	6	8	14	0.2027	0.652
Infrequent/Scanty bleeding	10	2	12	12.396	0.000*
Heavy menstrual bleeding	6	34	40	9.360	0.002*
Heavy and Prolonged bleeding	7	17	24	0.106	0.744
Intermenstrual bleeding	5	5	10	0.599	0.438

*p < 0.05 – Statistically Significant

Ultrasound finding in Abnormal Uterine Bleeding:

All the 100 women were subjected to Ultrasound examination for endometrial thickness and uterine size. Among them, 67 women had normal size of uterus and 33 women had bulky

uterus. The mean endometrial thickness was 15.33mm with minimum of 8mm and maximum of 25mm. Statistically significant association was found between endometrial thickness and increasing Body Mass Index (BMI) with p value < 0.05 (Table 3)

Table 3: Association between Endometrial Thickness in AUB and BMI

Endometrial Thickness	BMI		Chi-square Value	p- value
	18.5 - 24.9 Kg/m ²	≥ 25 Kg/m ²		
≤ 10 mm	25	24	10.960	0.000*
> 10 mm	9	42		

*p < 0.05 – Statistically Significant

Histopathological finding In Abnormal Uterine Bleeding:

Around 26% of women with altered menstrual bleeding had simple hyperplasia without atypia, 14% had complex hyperplasia without atypia and 13% had complex hyperplasia with atypia (Fig 2). No significant association was found between increasing BMI and different histopathological finding in AUB (Table 4)

Figure 2: Histopathological finding of Endometrium in AUB: (n=100)

Table 4: Association between Histopathological finding in AUB and BMI

Histopathological finding	BMI		Total	Chi-square Value	p- value
	18.5 - 24.9 Kg/m ²	≥ 25 Kg/m ²			
Proliferative	8	10	18	0.575	0.448
Secretory	6	12	18	0.043	0.834
Simple	1	4	5	0.037	0.846

hyperplasia with atypia					
Simple hyperplasia without atypia	7	19	26	0.415	0.518
Complex hyperplasia with atypia	3	10	13	0.333	0.563
Complex hyperplasia without atypia	6	8	14	0.202	0.652
Disordered proliferative	3	3	6	0.167	0.682

Discussion:

The primary objective of the study was to compare the menstrual pattern, endometrial thickness and histopathological finding in AUB with BMI. This study proves that, women with excessive weight with increased BMI are more prone to have Abnormal Uterine bleeding. In this study, 66% of the women with abnormal uterine bleeding had BMI ≥ 25 Kg/m². Study done by Agarwal et al proved high incidence of AUB among Obese patients.¹⁰ Another study done by Nouri et al showed mean BMI of 32.63 ± 3.34 in AUB patients.¹¹

Heavy bleeding seen in 40% and heavy with prolonged bleeding in 24%. Study done by Rajani Vaidya et al, noted 39.1% complaints of heavy bleeding and 23.1% with prolonged bleeding, which is similar to our study.¹² Study done by Kumarasamy et al noted 68% with heavy bleeding and 30% with prolonged bleeding.⁸

Mean endometrial thickness in the present study was 15.33mm and similar finding was seen in study conducted among premenopausal women in Bengaluru with Mean ET of 17.06 mm.⁸ But, study done by Wise et al proved 26mm as mean endometrial thickness in AUB.³ Nouri et al studied the effect of pathological effect of increased BMI in Thickened Endometrium and suggested uterine wall hyperplasia can lead to AUB. In their study, 44% had bulky uterus, but in our study, only 33% of premenopausal women with AUB had bulky uterus.¹¹

Simple hyperplasia without atypia is the common histopathological finding in this study, Pilli et al¹³ and Vakiani et al¹⁴ also had similar finding. Jairajpuri et al reported Proliferative phase as commonest presentation.¹⁵ Endometrial samples of AUB showed variable histopathological finding from simple physiological to complex pathological lesion.

Several studies have proved that obese women are prone to have menstrual irregularities and they also recommended, besides treating the AUB by managing anemia and associated comorbidity, the management of AUB should also include achieving healthy body weight.^{16,17,18}

Limitation of the study includes smaller sample size and the effect of duration of Increased Body weight in AUB could not be assessed as it is a cross sectional study. Further studies can be planned with larger sample size with control groups to prove strong correlation between BMI and AUB.

Conclusion:

Globally, Obesity is considered as slow epidemic. The study showed definite association of increased BMI in AUB. Therefore, there is a need to recommend weight reduction in AUB management. Further, Counselling the affected women and general public about the effect of increased body weight in menstrual disorders would reduce the prevalence of Menstrual irregularities among women of all age group.

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